

HYDROGEN BASED NUCLEAR REACTION

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Abstract- In this paper a new and powerful nuclear reaction is presented. A nuclear fission-based reaction is done theoretically of Bismuth and Hydrogen molecules as a resultant of which Polonium is produced along with nuclei.

As if the nuclear energy produced in the process can be used in the extreme warfare condition. So, by reacting the two radioactive atoms, the energy produced can use for the same purpose. The energy produced by the fission process is nearly equivalent to 1.87×10^{19} J. The element bismuth is chosen for this reaction because it has availability more than other elements.

Keywords- Fusion reaction; High energy; Mass defect; Relativity.

1.0 Introduction

A new and powerful physics-based algorithm as nuclear reaction optimization (NRO) was shown. Between the nucleus and the neutron, the Gaussian walk and differential evolution operators employed for appropriate exploration in the (NFi) phase. Levy flight was used for random searching. Three engineering design optimization problems were solved as constrained Using NRO and the compared algorithms, evaluate functions. The outcomes showed that the proposed nuclear reaction optimization algorithm was a potential and powerful approach for global optimization. [1]

Theoretically, the fusion reactions of two stable nuclei with heavy ions were used to study the creation of the radionuclide ¹¹¹In. The study suggested the new reaction reacting of the reactants for the production of ¹¹¹In radionuclide, to explore the effects of different calculation codes and effects of nuclear parameters on the barrier and cross-sections of heavy-ion fusion distributions, to showcase the results were reliable, and to emphasize the importance of developing these studies in the development of new experiments. [2]

Studies on the effects of the radiation dose on devices and materials was seen on the paper. A new method, based on radiochromic film dosimetry, was introduced for realtime dose assessment in experiments to ensure radiation hardness. The method allowed for correlating the radiation dose at which devices were exposed to the radiation effects. Thus new dosimeter was able to be used in different radiation environments. [3]

Decay modes of the compound systems generated in $86\text{Kr} + 134,138\text{Ba} \rightarrow 220,224\text{U}^*$ reactions at eight excitation energies have been distinguished to explore the influence of shell closures and excitation energy. The mass distribution of the cross-sections has been estimated for the two compound systems by keeping their excitation energies the same. The range of the incident energy which shows the high probability of the compound nucleus process has been found. [4]

In the recent decades, nuclear fusion and nuclear fission has become a very useful source for the production of electrical energy. The paper proposed a study on importance of the objective of the Moroccan high school students about the nuclear fusion and the nuclear fission during their study. [5]

A comprehensive study of the density dependence of the H-mode power threshold PLH on the mega-amp spherical tokamak (MAST) is presented. Transitions at low densities are characterise. To investigate the possibility of a critical edge ion heat flux, transitions of different densities and neutral beam heating powers were analysed with the interpretative transport code TRANSP, revealing that the heat flux possesses a density dependence independent of the net power. [6]

Reactions were induced using α - particles, the only projectile available initially. With the development of accelerators the possibilities multiplied by changing the energy and mass of the projectile. Sometimes we can have more than two final products. Under special circumstances, more than two reactants is possible. Thus, fordistributed among all nucleons, forming a highly excited compound nucleus. The decay of the compound nucleus leads to the final products of the reaction. At very high energies the quarks and gluons inside nucleons become “free” for a short time forming the quark-gluon plasma. The study of high energy reactions with nuclei is very important for a better understanding of what happens during spectacular stellar explosions. The study of nuclear reactions at high energies allows obtaining information on the equation of state of nuclear matter. [7]

In nuclear astrophysics, many reaction models are frequently utilised, particularly for the nucleosynthesis of the light elements. The majority of nuclear processes necessary for star evolution take place at energies much below the Coulomb barrier. Due to this characteristic, the cross sections are incredibly tiny and nearly hard to quantify in a laboratory. We first go over low-energy scattering in general, and define the various cross sections required for reaction networks (essentially radioactive capture and transfer reactions). Different models are shown. Microscopic theories based on essential concepts, such as the complete description of the antisymmetrization between all nucleons and a nucleon-nucleon interaction. Microscopic models can be simplified by omitting the internal structure of the colliding nuclei, which leads to the potential model, also dubbed the optical model. The phenomenological R-matrix theory is a different method for theoretically analysing the experimental data. In this method, the parameters are fitted to the data in order to extrapolate the cross sections down to stellar energy. The Trojan horse strategy and other indirect strategies were briefly described. Indirect approaches, such as the Trojan horse method, were briefly outlined. [8]

2.0 Explanation

- **Characterstics of reactants:**

Bi – It is a group 15 element with atomic mass 208.980 and atomic number 83.

Its melting point is 271.406 °C with boiling point 1564 °C and density (g cm³) 9.79. The key isotopes are Bi²⁰⁹ and electronic configuration can be written as [Xe] 4f145d106s26p3.

H - It is a group 1 element with atomic mass 1 and atomic number 1. Its melting point is -259.20 °C with boiling point -252.77 °C and density (g cm³) 0.0867 g/cm³. The key isotopes are hydrogen oxide, deuterium oxide, tritium oxide. And electronic configuration can be written as [H] 1s1.

- **Characterstics of products:**

Po - It is a group 16 element with atomic mass 207.98125 and atomic number 84.

Its melting point is 254 °C with boiling point 962 °C and density (g cm³) 9.30 at 20 °C. Polonium has 42 isotopes and electronic configuration can be written as [Hg] 6p4. Half -life is 2.898 years.

Neutron – spin ½, mass- 1.674, statistics – fermionic

Beta+ Ray-

- **Reaction:**

The above reaction is of a nuclear fusion reaction, it clearly shows that Bismuth atom is bombarded with hydrogen atom, as the resultant of which Polonium and a neutron is produced and the energy is given out in form of β^+ ray.

3.0 Energy Calculation:

The energy calculated through the theory of relativity, ($E=mc^2$) is,

$$1\text{amu.} = 931 \text{ MeV}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total mass of reactant} &= (209.656 + 2.0156)\text{u} \\ &= 211.6716\text{u} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total mass of product} &= (208.6544 + 1.0086)\text{u} \\ &= 209.663\text{u} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{So, defect in mass} &= (211.6716 - 209.663)\text{u} \\ &= 2.0086\text{u} \end{aligned}$$

$$E = 1871.01 \text{ MeV}$$

3.1 Comparison:

By using change in mass to calculate energy released,

$$\begin{aligned} 208.9804 - 208 \\ &= 0.9804 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Therefore, } 0.9804 * (3*10^8)^2 \\ &= 8.82 * 10^{16} \end{aligned}$$

The Tsar bomb releases 2.0×10^{17} joules.

10^{12} calories = 1 Kilotonneof TNT

For, the estimated energy released the amount of T.N.T. to be used in case is given as.

For 88 EJ of energy 21,500 MT T.N.T. is used,

Therefore, for 280.5 EJ energy to be released 68531.199 MT of T.N.T. should be used.

Equivalently, for 15 MT gives 280 EJ of energy,

Therefore, for 1 MT it comes out to be 18.66 EJ.

By using unitary method, it can be calculated as.

68531.199 MT OF T.N.T. is equivalent to 15 MT of fuel.

For, 1 MT of fuel 4,568.74 MT of TNT would be equivalent for it.

Fig1. The above graph presents the comparison of energy released of different nuclear bombs.

3.3 Threshold Energy:

It is the minimum energy that must be possessed by reactant molecules in order to give the products.

$$K_{th} = \frac{(M_Y + m_y)^2 c^2 - (M_X + m_x)^2 c^2}{2 \cdot M_x}$$

$$= \frac{(207.98 + 1.008)^2 \cdot (3 \cdot 10^8)^2 - (207.97 + 1.008)^2 \cdot (3 \cdot 10^8)^2}{2 \cdot 207.97}$$

$$= 2.17 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ MeV}$$

M_Y is the mass of the product nucleus
 m_y is the mass of the product particle
 M_X is the mass of the parent nucleus
 m_x is the mass of the projectile particle.

4.0 Conclusion:

The paper presents a powerful nuclear reaction through which tremendous amount of energy will get released and it can be used for the desired purpose. The defect in mass comes out to be 0.9804 which when converted in electron volt comes out to be 912.75 eV. The energy when calculated with the help of theory of relativity (formula) gives 1.87×10^{19} J. The calculations can be further elaborated in the, form of finding the different parameters of the reaction like, barrier potential of the nucleus

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